

Polarographic Studies on the Interaction of Furylamine with Copper(II) and Indium(III)

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Polarographic studies on Cu^{II} and In^{III} in presence of furylamine have been carried out at constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.10$). The reductions are diffusion-controlled in all cases. In case of Cu^{II} the reduction process is quasi-reversible which becomes reversible in the presence of complexing agent. The reversible half-wave potential for Cu^{II} in NaClO₄ has been determined by modified Gelling's method. The stability constants and composition of the complexes have been calculated by the method De-Ford and Hume as modified by Irving, Mihailov's mathematical method and Lingane's method. Cu^{II} forms two complexes, the first being extremely weak. The reduction process in case of In^{III}-furylamine system is non-reversible. The $E_{1/2}^r$ and kinetic parameters are calculated by modified Gelling's method. The values of standard rate constant (K_s) show that the irreversibility decreased with increase in the ligand concentration. The value of overall formation constants (4.0738×10^{19}) determined by Lingane's method, show strong complexation.

COMPLEXES formed by heterocyclic compounds containing nitrogen as hetero atom with metal ions have been studied by polarographic technique extensively¹. However, the survey of literature reveals limited studies on metal complexes with heterocyclic compounds containing oxygen as hetero atom. The literature reports the polarographic behaviour of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Cu^{II} with 2-furoate ions and with furan 2,5-dicarboxylate ions² and the interaction of 2-furoate ion with Zn^{II}, Eu^{III} and In^{III}, at d.m.e.³. The stepwise stability constants of complexes of furylamine with Ag^I at glass electrode in potassium nitrate medium have been studied by Gomick⁴. Polarographic studies on the complexes of furylamine and 2-aminopyrimidine with Cd^{II} and 2-furylacrylate ions with Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} have been carried out by the authors⁵.

The present communication reports the electrochemical behaviour of furylamine with Cu^{II} and In^{III}. The polarographic characteristics, composition and stability constants of the complexes with Cu^{II} have been investigated. Kinetic parameters of the electrode process for In^{III}-furylamine system have been reported.

Experimental

A manual polarographic set-up was used for obtaining C-V curves. The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics: $m=1.7645$ mg s⁻¹ and $t=3.645$ (at -0.0 V vs S.C.E. in 0.1M NaClO₄). The measurements were made at a constant temperature (303 K). Solution of furylamine in double-distilled water was used as complexing agent. Solutions containing 0.5 mM Cu^{II} or In^{III} and various concentrations of the complexing

agent were prepared at a constant ionic strength (0.10 M), maintained by the addition of requisite amount of sodium perchlorate solutions. The dissolved oxygen from the solutions was removed by passing purified nitrogen for 20-25 min.

Results and Discussion

In each case, a single well-defined wave has been observed. The plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} are linear and pass through origin showing that the reductions are diffusion-controlled. The complexation with the ligand is evident from the shift in the half-wave potential towards more negative values and the decrease in the diffusion currents with the increasing ligand concentration.

Cu^{II}-furylamine system: The $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log i/(i_d-i)$ plots were found to be linear with the slope for simple metal ion Cu^{II} in NaClO₄ ($\mu=0.10$) of the order of 31 ± 2 mV. It was concluded from these observations that the reduction of Cu^{II} in non-complexing media is a quasi-reversible process, which becomes reversible in the presence of complexing agent. The value of $E_{1/2}^r$ for Cu^{II} in NaClO₄ was determined by modified method of Gelling⁶ from the observed $E_{1/2}$ value by plotting $\left(E = \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{i_d-i}{i}\right)$ against i and by extrapolating it to $i=0$. The nature of these plots is straight line parallel to the current axis in complexing media; the value of $E_{1/2}^r$ was thus found to be identical with the observed $E_{1/2}$ values in such cases.

The plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log C_x$ gives a straight line indicating that the value of p is 2 (Fig. 1). Modified DeFord and Hume's method was applied to deter-

 Fig. 1 Plots of $E_{1/2}^r$ vs $-\log C_x$

mine the stability constants of the complexes formed⁷. The polarographic characteristics together with F_0 ($[X]$) values are given in Table 1. The

 TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS, F_0 ($[X]$) VALUES AND STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR 0.5 mM Cu^{II} -FURYLAMINE SYSTEM

Temp = 303 K		$\mu = 0.1 M (\text{NaClO}_4)$	
C_x mole	$E_{1/2}^r$ (V vs SCE)	i_d μA	F_0 ($[X]$)
0.00	+0.018 0 ^a	6.448	—
0.15	+0.015 0	5.824	1.394
0.20	+0.008 0	5.720	2.830
0.25	+0.003 0	5.408	4.069
0.30	-0.002 0	5.408	5.531
0.40	-0.007 5	5.356	8.517
0.50	-0.013 0	5.304	13.140

^a $E_{1/2}^r = E_{1/2}^r$

plots of F_1 ($[X]$) vs C_x extrapolated to zero ligand concentration showed the presence of only two complexes (Fig. 2). The values of the stability constant reveal that the first complex is extremely weak. However, the value of formation constant of the second complex has been calculated by Lingane equation⁸. The formation constants were also calculated by Mihailov's method as explained in an

 Fig. 2 Plots of F_j ($[X]$) vs C_x

earlier paper⁹. The values of the stability constants obtained by the three methods are summarised in Table 2. These values are quite close to one another. The percentage composition of various complexes species is presented in Fig. 3.

 TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES OF Cu^{II} -FURYLAMINE SYSTEM

Complex	DeFord-Hume	Mihailov	Ligane
$\text{Cu}(\text{Furylamine})_2^{2+} \beta_1$	1.00	1.32	—
$\text{Cu}(\text{Furylamine})_2^{2+} \beta_2$	45.50	41.64	43.15

 Fig. 3. Plots of % distribution vs $-\log C_x$.

In^{III}-furylamine system: The plots of $\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ are linear but the slopes come to be of the order of 30 ± 2 mV, which is higher than that required for three-electron reduction, showing non-reversible nature of the reduction process. The reversible half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}^r$) were determined by Gelling's method. The plots of $\left[E - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{i_d - i}{i} \right]$ vs i for *In*^{III} and *In*^{III} containing furylamine in 0.1 M NaClO_4 are presented in Fig. 4. Plot of $\log(z-1)$ vs $(E - E_{1/2}^r)$ should give a straight line as shown in Fig. 5. From the slope and intercept of this plot the value of α and K_s are calculated by modified Gelling's method (Table 3).

The plot of $E_{1/2}^r$ vs $-\log C_x$ is a smooth curve (Fig. 1). The value of p (co-ordination number) determined from the equation,

$$\frac{\Delta E_{1/2}^r}{\Delta \log C_x} = -\frac{p}{n} 0.06,$$

comes out to be approximately 6. The value of the overall formation constant, determined from Lingane equation, comes out to be 4.0738×10^8 . The attempt to evaluate formation constants by DeFord and Hume's method was not successful.

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR In^{III} -FURYLAMINE SYSTEM
 $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M (NaClO}_4\text{)}$
 Temp. = 303 K

C_x mole	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs S.C.E.)	$E_{1/2}^r$	i_d μA	α	λ $\text{s}^{1/2}$	$D^{1/2}$ $\times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	K_s $\times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$
0.00	0.543 0	0.539 0	5.252	0.355	1.383 6	0.003 1	4.289
0.10	1.224 0	1.207 5	4.420	0.375	0.415 2	0.002 6	1.079
0.15	1.232 0	1.215 0	4.368	0.355	0.433 7	0.002 6	1.127
0.20	1.261 0	1.224 5	4.368	0.311	0.176 8	0.002 6	0.459
0.25	1.264 5	1.235 5	4.342	0.334	0.262 9	0.002 6	0.683
0.30	1.256 0	1.246 0	4.316	0.334	0.262 9	0.002 5	0.657
0.35	1.280 0	1.256 5	4.290	0.311	0.324 5	0.002 5	0.811

Fig. 4. Plots of $-[E - \frac{RT}{nF} \log \frac{i_d - i}{i}]$ vs i .

Fig. 5. Plots of $(E_{1/2}^r - E)$ vs $\log(z-1)$.

It is evident from the values of standard rate constant (K_s) that the irreversibility decreased with the increase in the ligand concentration.

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